

“Who?”

Locating Joyce’s Transnational Women

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From the question-word incipit of *Giacomo Joyce*, a text unfolds that is all glance and afterimage, its central female figure evoked through epiphanic accumulation yet never explicitly named. “Who?” (*GJ* 1) functions less as question than as summons—is less interrogative than incantatory. And yet, from the moment of the work’s publication, readers have been encouraged to treat this beginning not as literary invocation but as biographical cue: to follow the question back to a presumed origin in lived experience, as if the opener were an endpoint and the task to recover what preceded it. For decades, Richard Ellmann’s identification of the subject with one of Joyce’s young pupils in Trieste has provided a fragile consensus for the field, cohering the work’s fragments around a single historical referent. That impulse to name is not misguided. It arises from an awareness that character construction in Joyce is intimately bound up with the biographism that informs so much of his work—that his writing is entangled with the social and material lives that surrounded its making. At the same time, Joyce studies’ prevailing identification reflects the limitations of midcentury archival access and the biases of early reception as much as the figure in the text. The question “Who?” is thus not only a textual gesture but also, considered across Joyce’s oeuvre, a methodological provocation: what happens when the women who pass through Joyce’s writing have lived across borders and moved between languages, leaving uneven traces? How do we identify Joyce’s transnational women when the historical record is so partial and what remains is scattered across jurisdictions, languages, and archival regimes?

Joyce studies has a problem with the real-life counterparts of Joyce’s female characters, with midcentury guesswork and back-of-the-envelope identifications exerting an outsize influence on literary history and biography. This problem is exacerbated in the case of women acquaintances of Joyce who experienced multistage transnational migration and whom he chose to Hibernicize in his writing. This article takes up that problem by bringing critical attention to four women whose lives and migrations intersected with Joyce’s own over several decades and across multiple countries: Suzanne McKernan Hughes, Gertrud Gradowski, Bice Ricchetti Randegger, and Gisella Norbedo Santas.¹ One of these women, Ricchetti Randegger, did not appear in the biographical record until 2020; another, Norbedo Santas, is scarcely documented, with the little that is known about her casting her chiefly in the role of her husband’s wife. McKernan Hughes and Gradowski, by contrast, appear briefly in successive editions of the Ellmann biography, offered as the primary model for Gerty MacDowell. And yet, all four women remain peripheral to the interpretive frameworks through which Joyce’s life and work are typically read. That marginality is not incidental. Each experienced multistage transnational migration. Most spoke or corresponded in multiple languages or a language other than English. All moved between cultural, professional, and geographic contexts that resist easy absorption into prevailing critical narratives.

What unites them, beyond their limited visibility in Joyce's biography, is the methodological challenge they pose. These women appear intermittently in the archive, often in fragmentary or highly mediated forms: as recipients of inscribed copies of Joyce's work; named in compositional notes for *Ulysses* or *Finnegans Wake*; refracted through misremembered anecdote; or listed in passenger manifests and vital records from multiple countries. This uneven presence calls for a form of critical attention attuned not only to degrees of resemblance between fiction and fact but also to the asymmetries that condition what is remembered and what is not—the linguistic, national, and disciplinary frameworks through which the lives of women on the move are unrecorded or irretrievable. By foregrounding these four women, this essay not only reframes how we read Joyce's female characters but also demonstrates that archival evidence can redirect biographical associations. My aim, however, is less to substitute one set of definitive identifications for another than to show how new archival findings recalibrate degrees of plausibility and to mark clearly the difference between documented association, likely derivation, interpretive inference, and biographers' projections. Rather than treating them as displaced referents of authorial creativity, I approach the four women as transnational subjects in their own right whose lived complexity both inscribes and obscures itself in the fiction. In what follows, I reconstruct the lives of McKernan Hughes, Gradowski, Ricchetti Randegger, and Norbedo Santas, situating them within the shifting contours of Joyce's transnational networks. I examine their presence—or absence—in the Joyce archive and in historical vital records to ask how their multilingual, mobile, and hybrid identities press against the conventions of literary biography. Finally, I consider what it means to read across borders and between languages in a field increasingly alert to multiple identifications and archival unevenness. In doing so, I aim to model a method of transnational recovery that takes seriously both the lure and the limits of biographical inquiry. The essay concludes by turning to Joyce's life partner, Nora Barnacle, to show that even the most central female figures remain vulnerable to archival precarity and the distorting pressures of biography.

Mobility has become something of a critical shorthand for Joyce's life and work, frequently invoked but rarely examined in relation to gendered experience. Epithets such as self-exiled artist, multilingual stylist, or restless cosmopolite read as an extension of authorial control: Joyce, the free-wheeling expat in pursuit of world literature, renders Dublin legible through a poetics shaped by continental forms, mainland European figures, and distance from home. This impression of Joyce as master navigator of transnational currents is central to the lifetime biographies, yet it risks occluding the gendered dynamics at work in those same pathways. In this mythologized account, Joyce moves deliberately through European capitals, absorbing languages and reinventing literature, while the women around him flicker in and out of view as patrons and publishers, lovers and near-*mâîtresses*, typists and translators—as fodder or foil to creative genius. This framework privileges a particular kind of movement (male, authorial, willed) and renders other mobilities incidental or invisible. Joyce's women moved, too, but their movement is more likely to be rendered biographically or creatively inert: an odyssey of the plus-one.

Joyce's transnationalism was never solitary. It was crowded, extractive, and dependent. The border-crossings of women in his orbit, whether by force, marriage, profession, illness, or war—many of the same circumstances that drove Joyce's own relocations—rarely receive the interpretive seriousness granted to his migrations. Where his movement is framed as generative, even mythic, theirs becomes background texture. To recast Joyce's

transnationalism is to recognize it as an ecology of dependency: a network of human enablers, many of them women, whose multilingualism, migratory lives, and intellectual labor were mobilized in the service of creative projects that largely elided them as historical agents, even as their lives, utterances, gestures, and very physiques were transmuted into the raw material of female character. These patterns of erasure are compounded by a persistent habit of Joyce studies: the search for real-life counterparts to his fictional characters. That impulse has given us Nora as Gretta Conroy, Lucia Joyce as Issy, and a host of minor acquaintances matched to fleeting characters on little more than intuition or the shaky testimony of Joyce's contemporaries.² Yet the history of these identifications is more contingent than conclusive. Much of what now passes for consensus emerged from midcentury speculation: a patchwork of memoir, anecdote, and inference that hardened, over time, into scholarly certainty. Where archival follow-up lagged or was slow to circulate, early provisional guesses calcified into orthodoxy. Revisiting that historiographical formation now is neither to dismiss the biographical impulse outright nor to disparage foundational scholarship in Joyce studies but, rather, to reconsider what it might mean to pursue identification when transnationalism, linguistic displacement, and archival unevenness are treated as primary rather than peripheral conditions.

Before turning to the four women whose transnational lives frame this study, it is worth noting that such speculative projection is not restricted to women alone. Alfred Henry Hunter (1866–1926), frequently proposed as one of the real-life models for Leopold Bloom, offers the paradigmatic male example.³ An Ulster Presbyterian who migrated to Dublin around the turn of the century, Hunter has long been treated less as a historical subject than as a biographical proxy or stand-in for Bloom. Following midcentury precedent (see *JJ* 162), biographies routinely present him as a Dublin Jew, despite his religious and regional background, retrofitting his identity to mirror the fictional character. Like the women discussed later, Hunter suffers from the critical habit of back-forming life from the work. He was not a transnational migrant but an internal one within Ireland—yet this proved sufficient to frustrate Ellmann's biographical efforts. Hunter's treatment serves as a reminder that the pursuit of fictional originals can flatten difference of all kinds and that gendered erasure, while pronounced, is not exclusive.⁴

SUZANNE MCKERNAN HUGHES

Born Susan McKernan into a Dublin shoemaker's family, Suzanne McKernan Hughes (1889–1972) grew up in Drumcondra, not far from the Joyce family's late-1890s residence on Richmond Avenue. As a young woman she moved to London to train at the Academy of Dramatic Art and, in 1921, acted as Susan Brady in a West-End production of *The Playboy of the Western World*. Later that year, she joined the Abbey Theatre breakaway company, the Irish Players, for their American tour of Lennox Robinson's *The White-Headed Boy*. She married the Belfast composer Herbert Hughes in New Jersey in January 1922 and relocated to London shortly thereafter, living in Chelsea for half a century.⁵ Joyce knew her first in Dublin, where their families lived close by, and reconnected with her in the expatriate networks of Paris and London during the late 1920s and 1930s. McKernan Hughes's layered identity—Irish by birth, cosmopolitan by profession—resists tidy national classification. Yet within Joyce studies, her memory has been flattened into a single speculative association: as one of the supposed models for Gerty MacDowell in “Nausicaa.”

One would imagine lived experience had connected Joyce with any number of people living with mobility impairment. Ellmann's identification originated in the 1939 Herbert Gorman biography, which set the stage with an anecdote about Joyce, in the afterglow of his *Fortnightly Review* coup, receiving William Archer's letter conveying Ibsen's praise. Gorman has Joyce sitting on a garden swing with an unnamed "young lady," both just returned from a dance, whose "attributes," he vaguely suggests, would later be absorbed into Gerty (69). Ellmann, improving on Gorman in the 1959 *James Joyce*, tightened the anecdote and supplied missing detail: the young lady became "Susie McKernan," and the undefined "attributes" solidified into "lameness," recast as "an aspect" of Gerty.⁶ The citation is to Gorman, but the elaboration is Ellmann's, drawn from a 1953 interview with Joyce's sister, Eileen Schaurek. It was she who claimed McKernan Hughes had a limp. Born in 1889, Eileen was recalling events from over half a century earlier—events she had witnessed as an eleven-year-old (if at all). The identification fails, however, on chronological grounds. McKernan would have been only ten years old in April 1900 when Joyce received Archer's letter—hardly an appropriate partner for a dance. This timeline renders Ellmann's elaboration of the anecdote untenable; still, matters might have rested there were it not for McKernan Hughes herself. In a letter to Ellmann following the publication of his Joyce biography, she left little room for doubt: "I am not and never was lame. I would be very interested to know how I became transfused into Gertie McDowall" [*sic*].⁷ Ellmann, to his credit, removed the identification from the 1965 paperback printing of *James Joyce*, but the episode lays bare the speculative foundations on which such identifications often rest—and the ease with which anecdote can slide into biographical fact.⁸

The irony is that McKernan Hughes left a far more substantial trace than most of the women who moved in Joyce's orbit, appearing in playbills, theatrical notices, and published memoir—material signs of a public life. She was not lame, but she was distinctly physical, her "little continental hands," as the English artist Ambrose McEvoy called them, contrasting with Gerty's treatment-whitened "finely veined alabaster" mitts (*U* 13.89).⁹ Into old age, as her daughter Angela Hughes would later recall, she retained an "animal enjoyment of the sea and sun" (16)—an embodied exuberance worlds away from the fragility Ellmann conjured. Her theatrical ambition, nurtured by a mother whose own stage dreams had been thwarted, launched her career across Dublin, London, and New York. That she once lived close by the Joyces in Drumcondra is a matter of historical record, but it was in 1930s London at her Chelsea home, where Joyce was an occasional guest at parties and at-homes, that their acquaintance deepened and found its mature footing.¹⁰ For all this late-life sociability, it was their childhood proximity that became the stuff of biography and character identification. That biographical attention privileged this early, tenuous contact over the more substantial later relationship not only distorts the nature of their acquaintance but also misdirects the search for fictional parallels.

The case of McKernan Hughes reveals how readily the movements, bodies, and ambitions of transnational women become folded into authorial myth. Her real life was migratory, theatrical, and intellectually engaged, but this was overwritten by a narrative of physical impairment and fictional origin—one derived from childhood proximity and a biographers' echo chamber. That she corrected the record and yet remained half-attached to the role says less about her than about the critical infrastructure that mistakes inference for evidence and anecdote for foundation. Writing in 1954, Ellmann warned that art "lavishes on one man another's hair, or voice, or bearing, with shocking disrespect for individual identity" ("Backgrounds of *Ulysses*" 337). Yet this cautionary insight about the composite logic of character, delivered while the biography was still in progress, did little to restrain his own

efforts to match Joyce's fictional women to real-life counterparts. The gender bias behind "one man" does cultural work here: it casts male character as, by default, composite—assembled from a plurality of lives—while implying that women, by contrast, might be more directly and singularly recoverable. Molly, as we shall see, is the exception that proves the rule: long acknowledged as a composite construct, she has in recent years become ever more narrowly identified with Nora Barnacle—thanks, in large part, to the wave of biographical novels and biofictions that seek to reclaim her story. This uneven logic of referentiality—composite men, single-origin women—shaped not only interpretation but also the conditions of archival recovery. What biographers thought they saw in the fiction determined how and whether they went looking for real-world counterparts. What was in flux at the midcentury, however, was not so much the fictional referent as the historical record itself, with the people who lent Joyce hairdo or habitus reverse-engineered, in many cases, from his work to flesh and blood. Amalia Popper's case is emblematic in this respect. The problems with her identification, the capsule biography it spawned, and the back-formation from *Giacomo Joyce* that sustained both were pointed out by Helen Barolini as early as a 1969 essay in the *New York Review of Books*, but her critiques have largely been ignored or contradicted in the decades since.¹¹ Having tried McKernan Hughes on for size in his search for Gerty's real-life counterpart, Ellmann turned to a second contender—this one more obscure, more foreign, and, perhaps significantly, more amenable to the logic of fictional stand-in.

GERTRUD GRADOWSKI

When Ellmann removed the reference to McKernan Hughes's supposed mobility issue for the 1965 paperback *James Joyce*, he already had a better story waiting in the wings. At the center of that story was Gertrud Gradowski (later Kaempffer, 1890–1978), a Prussian medical student with whom Joyce was briefly infatuated in late 1917. Then still Gertrud Gradowski, she had just turned twenty-seven; he was going on thirty-six. Ellmann's initial contact came via James S. Atherton, who, after delivering a talk on Joyce in Manchester in the early 1960s, was approached by a friend of hers. Ellmann began corresponding with Gradowski—by then using her married name, Kaempffer—in 1962 and continued doing so for about a year. He sat on his findings for two decades, however, finally presenting them in 1982 in two versions: first, as a centenary lecture delivered at the Library of Congress; second, in the revised edition of the *James Joyce* biography. The lecture version is longer, more speculative, and conspicuously writerly. Joyce's pursuit of "Gertrud Kaempffer," as Ellmann names her apparently unaware that this was her married name, is framed as a kind of rehearsal or method acting for "Nausicaa," casting the trainee doctor as unwitting stimulus for fictional invention.¹² The emphasis is on narrative mirroring: Joyce lends her a copy of *A Portrait of the Artist as a Young Man*, praises her hands, proposes clandestine correspondence, and sends her sexually charged letters. Her inner life is barely registered. The Alpine flirtation becomes the staging ground for Gerty. In the biography, the framing is tighter, the tone more measured, and "Kaempffer's" perspective is slightly more foregrounded. She admires Joyce's mind, declines his overtures, and destroys the letters. But even here, she is instrumentalized: the hands she deems "thin and sickly" are transfigured into Gerty's alabaster ones; her discomfort with Joyce's advances is narrated as lost opportunity (*JJ* 418). Where the lecture dramatizes projection, the biography presents her as a type: subdued, naïve, unworldly—cast in relief against Joyce's knowingness.

Her actual life-story complicates this framing. Born in Neidenburg, East Prussia (present-day Nidzica, Poland), Gradowski was educated abroad and became the first female medical student at the University of Rostock (not “one of the first woman medical students in Germany,” as Ellmann has it [*JJ* 418]). Her studies carried her to Heidelberg, Breslau, Munich, and Würzburg. There she fell seriously ill with tuberculosis shortly after completing eight weeks of grueling final examinations—exceptional at a time when most students sat only abbreviated two-day wartime exams. Following the Russian invasion of East Prussia in 1914, her parents were forced to flee their homeland, and the Gradowski family spent the early years of the war moving her between Swiss sanatoria.¹³ It was during her convalescence in Locarno that Gradowski met Joyce.

On Christmas Eve 1917, he inscribed a copy of the *Egoist Portrait* to her “with the writer’s compliments”; a few weeks later, he sent on a copy of *Chamber Music* through an intermediary. The *Gradowski Portrait*, in particular, has “over thirty page numbers noted in pencil on the rear endpaper,” suggesting it was read closely—most likely by Gradowski herself.¹⁴ The two inscribed volumes only surfaced in the 1990s, in the decade after Ellmann’s reconstruction, revealing for the first time the name by which Joyce would have known her. Their delayed reappearance underscores the archival contingency of female presence in Joyce studies: how even women who enter the biographical record can leave behind traces that emerge too late to shape their reception. Indeed, following Ellmann’s lead, critics continue to refer to Gradowski by her married name—a minor error that nonetheless disrupts the likely link between her birth surname and the surname of Gerty MacDowell and reflects a broader pattern in literary biography, whereby an initial misnaming hardens into convention and resists subsequent correction, even when the archival record has shifted.¹⁵ Women in the historical record are particularly vulnerable to this kind of nominal drift. With Gradowski’s surname now restored, Joyce’s Hibernicizing adaptation of it as “MacDowell” comes into view for the first time.

That Gerty MacDowell is, in all likelihood, named for Gertrud Gradowski aligns with a broader pattern in Joyce’s work of naming fictionalized love interests after real-life counterparts. So, Emma Clery in *Stephen Hero* is named, as Peter Costello first argued, for Mary Elizabeth (M. E.) Cleary, a fellow student at University College, and Beatrice Justice in *Exiles* is named for Bice Ricchetti.¹⁶ But to list these examples is to imply overneat one-to-one equivalences—precisely the logic Ellmann had warned against, even as he occasionally pursued it by matching Joyce’s fictional women to individual real-life counterparts. Gerty herself, often taken as a singular construct, draws in minor details from other transnational women in Joyce’s orbit. For instance, Bloom’s observation that her wide-brimmed straw hat was “bought to hide her face” (*U* 13.838) derives from an entry in the “Nausicaa” notesheets: “Simone Brustlein’s hat hides face.”¹⁷ Brustlein (1895–1950), the Bern-born daughter of a prominent lawyer and politician, was known to Joyce through her sister Francine, with whom he corresponded on English Players matters.¹⁸ A sometime correspondent of Rilke, Simone spent time in England and the United States during the 1910s before emigrating to America with her future husband, Oskar Ziegler, in 1921. She became a naturalized American citizen in 1929.¹⁹ Her fleeting presence in the notesheets underscores how even minor traits or brief encounters—an accessory, a gesture—can find their way into Joyce’s characters, further disrupting the logic of reductive biographical equivalence.

Gradowski’s transnational identity complicates the pattern of naming fictionalized love interests after real-life counterparts. She was not Irish, Catholic, or provincial. She was a

Prussian medical graduate, German-speaking with some knowledge of English, educated across multiple universities, mobile, displaced by war, and, when Joyce met her, briefly resident in a multilingual spa town. Her transformation into Gerty MacDowell can be read as a study in Hibernization: the process by which Joyce's fiction domesticated foreign subjects—especially women—by reimagining them through the codes of Irish class and religious identity. This transformation is not simply a case of literary repurposing but an instance of cultural recontainment—where transnational difference is rewritten in the familiar idioms of Irish femininity and a foreign, credentialed professional becomes a localized Catholic object of longing, her geographic mobility in life recast as Gerty's mobility impairment. Ellmann's 1980s reconstruction echoes this logic: unable to accommodate Gradowski's linguistic, professional, and geographic complexity, he renders her legible instead as little more than the object of Joyce's tepid erotic pursuit.

BICE RICCHETTI RANDEGGER

Whereas Gradowski entered the record through personal testimony, Bice Randegger *née* Ricchetti (1887–1964) surfaced through flyleaf inscriptions. In summer 2019, presentation copies of Joyce's first three books came to light after decades of warehouse storage and went to auction in London, drawing scholars' attention to their provenance.²⁰ All three were addressed to the same recipient and bore the version of her name Joyce used: Beatrice. They turned out to be association copies—inscribed to a woman absent from the biographical record but closely connected to the author. Signed over an eight-year period, the volumes did more than enlarge the known circle of Joyce's students; they redirected a long-standing biographical identification. For decades, Amalia Popper has stood as the presumed "Beatrice" of *Giacomo Joyce* (*GJ* 11)—not because the evidence was strong, but because Ellmann enshrined her in the role early on. Others followed his lead, drawing on the authority of the canonical biography and in the absence of a better candidate.²¹ The surfacing of these volumes offers not just a counterclaim but a serious corrective to the prevailing identification.²²

A Trieste native, Bice Ricchetti was born into the city's Germanophone Jewish elite. The family name was officially "Richetti," though her father, Ettore, a lawyer, shipyard director, and prominent irredentist, favored the spelling with two c's. The Ricchettis lived in the city center before relocating to a villa in the hillside Scorcola district, an affluent residential area well within reach of her English teacher. Bice studied with Joyce from 1911 to 1913; on her twenty-fourth birthday, October 25, 1911, he inscribed a copy of *Chamber Music* to his pupil. In December of the following year, Bice fell ill with acute appendicitis and underwent emergency surgery at the Sanatorio Triestino private clinic. In February 1914, she married Henry Victor Randegger, an English national born and raised in Trieste. Joyce presented her with a copy of *Dubliners* four months later, inscribed with her married name. War intervened. As British nationals in Austro-Hungarian territory, the Randegggers were arrested at Feldkirch while attempting to leave the Dual Monarchy and interned in Raabs, Austria. Immediately after the Armistice, Ricchetti Randegger returned to Trieste where, a year later, Joyce, himself back from Zurich, inscribed a copy of *A Portrait* to her.²³

The arc of Ricchetti Randegger's biography closely parallels that of the beloved in *Giacomo Joyce*: student, inpatient turned convalescent, bride. As Erik Schneider has argued, point for point, she emerges as the most persuasive match yet for the woman addressed in the text.²⁴ For example, the Ricchetti villa, perched above the city, stood just uphill from Joyce's

lessons at the Ralli residence (see *GJ* 15); photographs of Ettore Ricchetti match the “long white whiskers” of *Giacomo Joyce*’s fictional patriarch (*GJ* 5); and the family’s divided loyalties as irredentist shipbuilders to the imperial navy echo Joyce’s aphorism: “They love their country when they know which country it is” (*GJ* 9). The detail of Bice’s appendectomy, which Schneider has confirmed from hospital records, is a rare instance of real-world surgery aligning precisely with textual speculation (see *GJ* 11).²⁵

Ricchetti Randegger’s return to the record via flyleaf rather than anecdote clarifies the limits of a field that too often mistakes priority for historical proof. What sets her apart is not just the density of archival traces, but the refusal of tidy equivalence. This resistance registers in the text itself, where Joyce twice invokes a literary-historical Beatrice, Shelley’s and Dante’s (*GJ* 11), to insert Bice under his preferred name for her. Her presence in *Giacomo Joyce* is, I would argue, both unmistakable and unstable: a slyly named figure caught between inscription and interpolation, between the certainty of multiple book dedications and the uncertainty of fragmentary representation. Like Gradowski, Ricchetti Randegger received a copy of *Chamber Music* early in her acquaintance with Joyce—incribed not just personally but, one imagines, propositionally. And like Gradowski’s, her copy was inaccessible to scholars for decades. The two sets of signed volumes, evidence of both association and Joyce’s fictional naming practice, resurfaced only in the last thirty years. That delay is not incidental. It exemplifies the evidentiary lag that shadows the recovery of transnational women, where presence in the archive does not guarantee acknowledgment in literary history or a place in critical memory. With her name now newly resonant, Ricchetti Randegger turns out to have been hiding in plain sight: a wish list of prospective subscribers to the Shakespeare and Company *Ulysses* in Joyce’s hand includes “Mrs Beatrice Randegger,” with an address given as the very villa on Pendice di Scorcola where he once taught her. When the list appeared in facsimile in a 1987 edition of Joyce’s letters to Sylvia Beach, the significance of the name went unremarked and unrecognized.²⁶ Recovery is rarely linear: biographical meaning often emerges only through cumulative returns to the archive, and what was once considered peripheral can, over time, reorient the field.

The new identification has implications not only for *Giacomo Joyce* but also for *Exiles* and Joyce’s poetry of the 1910s, where elusive Bice-like figures recur without a clear referent. In Ellmann’s biography and those that followed it, Ricchetti Randegger is wholly absent—her place and importance retroactively assigned to Popper. The final case study presents a related challenge: a figure named in passing but who remains just beyond recognition, visible yet unacknowledged.

GISELLA NORBEDO SANTAS

If McKernan Hughes and Gradowski stand, however tentatively, for a particular speculative tradition within Joyce studies and Ricchetti Randegger only entered the biographical record in the last few years, Gisella Santas, born Norbedo (1880–1938), occupies a different position: scarcely remembered at all, except fleetingly, as yet another candidate in the long-standing game of identifying “the real Molly Bloom.” That interpretive impulse had its start in Joyce’s own lifetime; the 1939 *James Joyce* credits Lillian Wallace’s repetition of the word “yes” for, in Gorman’s phrase, “the motif word” of the “Penelope” episode (281).²⁷ In an approach that privileges one-to-one biographical correspondences for female characters—despite Ellmann’s own acknowledgment of character as composite—Molly is the exception. In his *James Joyce*

alone, the list of contributory women is expansive: not only Nora, Wallace, and the ubiquitous Popper, but also Mary Tallon Chance, a concert soprano; the voluptuous wife of a fruit seller whom Ellmann names “Nicolas Santos”; and, for Molly’s “Spanish quality,” one of the “many daughters of Matt Dillon” (*JJ* 375–76). Six women to make a Molly. Within this select company, Norbedo Santos represents a missed opportunity. A woman whose multiple intersections with Joyce’s life go largely unexamined, she registers as little more than a stylized silhouette in the main biography: curvaceous and domestic. Her most detailed mention in *James Joyce* comes not as biography but as a speculative sidelight on character origins, where Ellmann proposes that Molly’s persona is “closer to that of the buxom wife of a fruit store owner named Nicolas Santos [*sic*], with whom [Joyce] was acquainted in Trieste and in Zurich. Signora Santos stayed indoors all day to preserve her complexion, for which she mixed her own creams. That Mrs. Santos had a share in Mrs. Bloom was an open secret in the Joyce family later” (*JJ* 375–76). Earlier in the biography, the same person is reduced to “a buxom wife” (*JJ* 268).²⁸ These nods are cursory and oblique: Norbedo Santos remains unnamed, partially described, and folded into a generalized type.

The notesheets for “Penelope” offer a suggestive lead: the entry “N.B. & Mrs Santos” (494) aligns Norbedo Santos with, presumably, Nora Barnacle. Rather than a vague type, the Joyces’ Triestine acquaintance appears here as a named compositional reference. That this pairing has gone largely unremarked reveals how narrowly such archival traces can be read—and how easily women without a strong biographical scaffold are overlooked. Schneider and I have been able to fill in details of Ellmann’s fragmentary portrait, building on archival work undertaken by Manto Aravantinou in the 1970s.²⁹ A native of Istria (then part of the Austro-Hungarian Empire), Gisella Norbedo married Nikolas Santos in Trieste in 1909.³⁰ Catholic and Greek Orthodox, respectively, theirs was an interfaith marriage along the lines of the Blooms’ in *Ulysses*—even if more socially legible in prewar Trieste than the fictive Edwardian Dublin. The chronology is revealing, however: Joyce’s unwritten “Ulysses” short story predates any known connection between Norbedo and Santos and cannot plausibly be drawn from their relationship. In summer 1915, with war on their doorstep, the Santases left Trieste and traveled by train—as the Joyces would a month later—through the Austro-Hungarian interior to Switzerland.³¹ In the 1910 Triestine census, a boy named Carilo, close in age to Giorgio, appears in their household as a nephew; five years later, in Zurich, he is recorded as their son.³² The discrepancy suggests not deception but adaptation: the pragmatism of migrant families navigating national boundaries, linguistic pluralism, and the opportunities afforded by bureaucratic do-over. The Santases did not stay long in Zurich. By late 1915, they had relocated to Genoa, which explains Frank Budgen’s skewed account of Nikolas in *James Joyce and the Making of “Ulysses,”* since Budgen never met the family.³³ By 1917, the Santases were living in Barcelona; four years later, they moved again, this time to Marseille. Over the course of a few years, Gisella of Trieste became Gisela in wartime Zurich, then Gisèle in the Western Mediterranean—a sequence that registers not simply personal reinvention but a broader arc of cultural reorientation and integration. Santos held a diploma in dressmaking, spoke and wrote in multiple languages, and was actively seeking work in Barcelona in early 1922.³⁴

The Joyces kept up with the Santases. They reconnected during the family’s brief stay in Zurich and remained in contact after both parties had left Switzerland. A letter from Nikolas to Joyce in Trieste, sent from Barcelona in April 1920, is now held at Cornell.³⁵ Another of the subscriber wish lists for *Ulysses*, now at the University at Buffalo, includes Nikolas’s name and Marseille address.³⁶ And in October 1922, while passing through the French port city,

Joyce and Nora visited the Santas family. Joyce wrote to Beach, “Penelope is here and flourishing. I had not seen her for eight years” (*JJSB* 14). The remark is unambiguous, indicating that Joyce himself was willing to identify Gisella with Molly’s Homeric counterpart—even if only as one among several shaping presences. Yet despite the clarity of the lead, no one before Aravantinou appears to have taken it up. Norbedo Santas remained an aside: named but unexamined, present but critically unpursued.

The impression of Norbedo Santas that emerges from the Joyce biographies is that of a voluptuous, sedentary figure, vain of her appearance. Two traits recur: she stayed indoors all day to preserve her complexion, mixing her own creams; and she embodied the physicality later attributed to Molly. This stylized image—suggestive of domestic vanity and class pretension—sits uneasily alongside a documented life of movement and labor. Between 1915 and 1922, Norbedo Santas crossed borders, shifted linguistic regimes, sought employment, and traveled with her husband and a young in-law across the unstable geographies of wartime Mitteleuropa and the Mediterranean. The anecdotal portrait of her as a stay-at-home cosmetics mixer (perhaps back-formed from Molly) is not evidence but atmosphere, a decorative shorthand that confirms rather than complicates the literary image. Placed against the archival record, it risks collapsing into gendered caricature: an ornamental figure mistaken for a historical subject.

This disjunction exemplifies a broader tendency in midcentury Joyce studies to reduce the women in Joyce’s orbit, beyond the anointed few, to fragments of flesh and setting, interchangeable types rather than discrete historical agents. That both Popper and Norbedo Santas—one a student twentysomething, the other a married migrant—have been cited as sources for Molly’s Southern European appearance underscores how easily women of different ages, classes, and geographies can be folded into the same vaguely exoticized template. There is something decidedly off in the abiding image of the buxom fruit-seller’s wife: it mirrors the reductive perspectives through which Molly herself is mediated in the *Odyssey* episodes of *Ulysses*. Even Brenda Maddox reproduces the gesture, writing that Molly got her “*embonpoint* from another in Trieste,” as if figure alone were enough to anchor character.³⁷ In such readings, accomplished women who crossed borders are reduced to body parts or bodily impairment.

Part of this distortion is archival. A multilingual migrant woman, Norbedo Santas left little in obvious places for midcentury biographers to work with. But the fixation on her body brings us close to what Marina Warner, describing the “slipped chiton” or exposed breast in visual culture, identifies as “not being introduced to the body as person.”³⁸ The mammary figuration haunts not only painting but also literary history. It asks us to reconsider what we think we recognize in women who were seen, briefly, through the eyes of Joyce and for far longer through the lenses of his critics. This impulse to monumentalize—to reduce a woman to a phrase like “buxom wife”—risks rendering Norbedo Santas not simply misrecognized but immobilized: no longer a migrant figure in motion, but a statue cast in place or image suspended. Against this freeze-frame, the record of her multilingual and geographic mobility and her economic participation offers a more dynamic counter-image: a life in motion that resists the static femininity imposed by biography.

Norbedo Santas’s significance lies less in the epiphanic frisson of single encounter than in sustained decades-long acquaintance. Unlike other women who flicker through Joyce’s life, she appears first in Trieste, where the Joyces and Santases were friendly neighbors; resurfaces during the two families’ overlapping time in Zurich; and is last glimpsed in Marseille, when Joyce and Nora visited in late 1922—present not as muse, collaborator, or helpmeet but as part

of his social and migratory world. That Joyce explicitly referred to her as “Penelope” ought to have prompted greater critical interest. That it did not speaks less to her role in the fiction than to the difficulty of tracking her through the archive. Her multilingual domestic life, her interfaith marriage, and her repeated cross-border relocations resist assimilation into a biographical model committed to coherence and tidy narrative logic at the expense of the lived complexity of those around Joyce.

* * *

This essay has traced a set of women whose names, biographies, and archival traces remain peripheral to the frameworks through which we read Joyce’s life and fiction. It has proposed a method of transnational recovery that takes seriously both the pull of biographical interpretation and the archival, historical, and methodological limits that constrain it. The lives of Suzanne McKernan Hughes, Gertrud Gradowski, Bice Ricchetti Randegger, and Gisella Norbedo Santas do not resolve into neat fictional origins; they are not missing muses to be “found” and slotted into pre-existing critical paradigms. Rather, they expose the friction between biographical desire and evidentiary constraint and highlight the degree to which interpretation is shaped by what has been preserved, misremembered, or left out.

What the four case studies offer, then, is not closure but context. That these women’s lives were rendered illegible by midcentury biography is not incidental but structural: their transnational movements and multilingual identities confounded the stabilizing imperatives of character identification and authorial mythmaking. The very gaps and distortions in their reception point to larger patterns in Joyce studies: reliance on early and anecdotal authority, pursuit of singular referents, and the slow uptake of transnational frameworks in biographical scholarship. To read across borders and between languages is not only to follow Joyce’s own itineraries but also to attend to the conditions that govern preservation and visibility in the first place. Such an approach does not aim to re-center these women within a singular narrative of artistic origin but, rather, to reframe the field itself: to ask how women might be better represented in Joyce biography if it foregrounded not muses and models but the fragmentary traces of transnational lives. In an age when digitized newspapers and searchable vital records have made it easier than ever to backfill speculative identifications—each new claimant insisting that a relative, a name plucked from *Thom*’s, or some Dublin shopkeep was the “real” Leopold Bloom or man in the mackintosh—this method resists biographical overreach. It does not treat these women as originals in search of a character, but as figures whose itinerant, multilingual lives trouble the terms of that search and unsettle the premises on which it so often rests.

CODA: NORA BARNACLE

“I rescued Nora from Special Collections,” writes Maddox in a retrospective account of researching *Nora: The Real Life of Molly Bloom*.³⁹ The line, meant to dramatize a biographer’s intervention, also testifies to the fragility of archival presence. Even for Joyce’s life partner, the record is patchy—shaped by contingencies and shadowed by known unknowns. One instance of this material slippage comes from Ellmann’s first European research trip in spring 1953, when he borrowed the “famous trunk” of Joyce family papers from Maria Jolas.⁴⁰ Among the materials were letters from Nora to her husband, which Ellmann dismissed in

correspondence with Jolas as “pathetic, over-sexed.” These letters appear to have since vanished. Zachary Leader, who brought this episode to light, suggests that the letters were those “Nora wrote in response to Joyce’s ‘dirty letters’ of 1909,” likely bundled with other correspondence she had passed on to Jolas in 1939, “in what Jolas called ‘a gesture of fatigue and helplessness.’”⁴¹ The familiar “dirty letters” written by Joyce were only one half of a “dirty correspondence.”

What Leader does not note is that, in the early 1950s, Ellmann had no access to Joyce’s side of the exchange—and, indeed, may not have realized that Joyce had written to his partner in the same vein. The “dirty letters” to Nora remained in Trieste, still in the vigilant custody of Stanislaus Joyce. It was only after Stanislaus’s death in 1955 that Ellmann gained access to Joyce’s side, and his tone shifted markedly. By 1975, he would describe the letters to Nora as “a turbulent mixture of erotic imagery and apologies for it,” part of Joyce’s attempt to renew “the conspiratorial and passionate understanding that they had had when they first left Ireland together” (*SL* xxiv). Nora’s responses, once pathologized in isolation, would no doubt have read differently in the fuller, two-sided context. That comparison is now likely impossible as Jolas passed the trunk to Giorgio Joyce and the letters may no longer survive; if destroyed, the timing and circumstances remain obscure.⁴²

The episode makes plain that legibility in the historical record depends not only on what survives, but on who is empowered to preserve, interpret, or dismiss the fragmentary. And if the women examined in this essay risk erasure through obscurity, Nora shows that even the most central female figures in Joyce’s life can be misread when the evidence is partial or lacking. Her case underscores the enduring precarity of archival transmission for transnational women—whose language, location, and material legacy so often disqualify them in advance.

NOTES

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1. The question of naming is not incidental. Joyce knew McKernan Hughes, Ricchetti Randegger, and Norbedo Santas on either side of marriage, and, particularly in the first two cases, their archival traces reflect this split-name acquaintance across both Joyce’s papers and the historical record. Ironically, the one woman he did not encounter after her marriage—Gertrud Gradowski—is routinely referred to in Joyce studies by her married name, Kaempffer. Such retrospective naming, whether through habitual reference to married names or the erasure of pre-marital identity, reinforces a broader pattern in literary biography: the standardization of women’s identities through marital status, which not only distorts but also structures the historical record, complicating efforts to connect unmarried and married traces of the same individual. After some deliberation, I ultimately adopt compound forms (e.g., McKernan Hughes, Ricchetti Randegger, Norbedo Santas) for the women known to Joyce under more than one name in order to account for the varied documentary footprints that they leave in the archive. The construction is anachronistic; none of them is known to have used blended forms of their names. But it serves to hold together biographical traces that are otherwise scattered across multiple contexts and jurisdictions.

2. Richard Ellmann was among the first to trace the parallels between Nora Barnacle’s recollection of a young admirer and the story Gretta tells of Michael Furey; see Ellmann, “The Backgrounds of ‘The Dead,’” *Kenyon Review* 20, no. 4 (Autumn 1958): 507, 518. This essay was later revised as Chapter XV of the Joyce biography (*JJ* 243–53). Michael Seidel, for example, develops the connection further, arguing that Joyce “minted for his fiction virtually every word, expression, motion made by his wife, Nora Barnacle, and displayed them in his key women characters, Gretta Conroy in

‘The Dead,’ Molly Bloom in *Ulysses*, and Anna Livia Plurabelle in *Finnegans Wake*. It was almost as if Nora Barnacle offered Joyce his body language”; Seidel, “James Joyce,” in *The Columbia History of the British Novel*, ed. John Richetti (New York: Columbia University Press, 1994). 777. For Lucia as Issy, see Carol Loeb Shloss, *Lucia Joyce: To Dance in the Wake* (New York: Farrar, Straus and Giroux, 2003), 10 and passim; or Genevieve Sartor, “Genetic Connections in *Finnegans Wake*: Lucia Joyce and Issy Earwicker,” *Journal of Modern Literature* 41, no. 4 (Summer 2018): 18–30.

3. Herbert Gorman, in his lifetime biography, noted the importance to Joyce of “some person he had known named Hunter” as the basis for the projected “Ulysses” short story. Harry Levin later conjectured that Hunter “must have been an Anglo-Irishman.” Ellmann was the first to offer a biographical sketch of Hunter, by way of Stanislaus Joyce, describing the Ulsterman as “tall and dark-faced, . . . supposed to be Jewish in spite of his name, which he had presumably changed”; see Gorman, *James Joyce* (New York: Farrar & Rinehart, 1939), 177; Levin, *James Joyce: A Critical Introduction* (Norfolk: New Directions, 1941), 84; Ellmann, “The Backgrounds of *Ulysses*,” *Kenyon Review* 16, no. 3 (Summer 1954): 379. Future citations to the Gorman biography will be indicated parenthetically in the text by page number. Future citations of Ellmann’s essay will be indicated parenthetically in the text as “Backgrounds of *Ulysses*,” followed by page number.

4. Stanislaus could not even tell Ellmann what Hunter’s given name was. This detail was first uncovered by Robert M. Adams, who spent the spring of 1960 in Dublin on a Guggenheim Fellowship, devouring historical newspapers; see Adams, *Surface and Symbol: The Consistency of James Joyce’s “Ulysses”* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1962), 62.

For more recent scholarship on Hunter, see Terence Killeen, “Myths and Monuments: The Case of Alfred H. Hunter,” *Dublin James Joyce Journal* 1 (2008): 47–53; and Marc A. Mamigonian, “Hunter and Gatherers: On the Trail of the *Dubliners* ‘Ulysses’ and Its Mysterious Hero,” *James Joyce Quarterly* 54, no. 1–2 (Fall 2016–Winter 2017): 13–31.

5. John Simpson, “Suzanne Hughes,” James Joyce’s Correspondence, June 13, 2022, <https://jamesjoycecorrespondence.org/>.

6. Richard Ellmann, *James Joyce* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1959), 77.

7. Suzanne Hughes to Richard Ellmann, April 21, 1960, quoted in Luca Crispi and Stacey Herbert, with Lori N. Curtis, *In Good Company: James Joyce & Publishers, Readers, Friends: An Exhibition of McFarlin Library’s Special Collections in Occasion of the North American James Joyce Symposium, University of Tulsa, 2003* (Tulsa, Okla.: University of Tulsa, 2003), 39.

8. See Richard Ellmann, *James Joyce* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1965), 77.

9. Ambrose McEvoy, quoted in Angela Hughes, *Chelsea Footprints: A Thirties Chronicle* (London: Quartet, 2008), 16. Future citations will be indicated parenthetically in the text by page number.

10. See David Crackanthorpe, “To Herbert Hughes of Belfast from James Joyce of Dublin,” *James Joyce Quarterly* 17, no. 2 (Winter 1980): 126–28, 132, 137.

11. See Helen Barolini, “The Curious Case of Amalia Popper,” *New York Review of Books* 13 (November 20, 1969): 44–48.

12. Richard Ellmann, *James Joyce’s Hundredth Birthday, Side and Front Views: A Lecture Delivered at the Library of Congress on March 10, 1982* (Washington, D.C.: The Library, 1982), 6, 8. Also issued as Ellmann, “Joyce at 100,” *New York Review of Books* 29, no. 18 (November 18, 1982): 58–65. For the second edition of James Joyce, Ellmann Englished Gradowski’s forename as “Gertrude” (*JJ* xiv and passim).

13. Gertrud Kaempffer to Richard Ellmann, January 13, 1963, Richard Ellmann Papers, University of Tulsa, McFarlin Library, Department of Special Collections & University Archives.

14. The two copies were offered in Jessy Randall and Glenn Horowitz, with Laura Barnes, *James Joyce: Books & Manuscripts* (New York: Glenn Horowitz Bookseller, 1996), 18.

15. A recent example: Andreas Fischer, typically so scrupulous in fact-checking Ellmann’s claims, nonetheless follows him in using Gradowski’s married name; see Fischer, *James Joyce in Zurich: A Guide* (Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2020), 43–44.

16. Peter Costello, *James Joyce: The Years of Growth, 1882–1915* (New York: Pantheon, 1992), 185, 187. The observation that Richetti is an Italianized form of Richter (“judge” in German) is Erik Schneider’s; Beatrice Justice’s surname suggests, then, not the abstract principle but a judicial function—an officer charged with the administration of law.

17. James Joyce, *Joyce's "Ulysses" Notesheets in the British Museum*, ed. Phillip F. Herring (Charlottesville: Published for the Bibliographical Society of the University of Virginia by the University Press of Virginia, 1972), 133. Future citations will be indicated parenthetically in the text by page number.

18. Joyce's letter to Francine Brüstlein, dated February 8, 1918, is in the James Joyce Collection, Harry Ransom Center, University of Texas at Austin. Joyce spelled the surname with the umlaut in his correspondence but dropped it in his private notes.

19. See Ingeborg Schnack, *Rainer Maria Rilke: Chronik seines Lebens und seines Werkes* (Frankfurt: Insel-Verlag, 1975), 700, 722. Additional information about Simone Brüstlein is taken from digitized vital records consulted on FamilySearch. <https://www.familysearch.org/>.

20. For details of provenance prior to sale, I am indebted to Erik Schneider (email to the author, February 7, 2022). For Bice Ricchetti Randegger's copy of *Chamber Music*, see *Items Displayed at Masterpiece, London, 27 June to 3 July 2019* (London: Peter Harrington, 2019), 57–59 (Item 32). For *Dubliners* and *A Portrait*, see *Fine Books, Manuscripts, and Works on Paper: Thursday 26th September 2019, The Westbury Hotel, Mayfair, London* (London: Forum Auctions, 2019), 60–62 (Lots 135–36).

21. See, for example, Eileen Lanouette Hughes, "The Mystery Lady of *Giacomo Joyce*," *Life* 64, no. 5 (February 2, 1968): 36–37, 40.

22. For early coverage of the discovery and its challenge to the Popper identification, see the interview with Schneider in Raffaele Oriani, "Quell'amore segreto di Joyce a Trieste," *Il Venerdì* (January 3, 2020): 96–99.

23. Biographical details of Ricchetti Randegger's early life and family background are drawn from research undertaken by Schneider; see "Being Bice: Bice Ricchetti Randegger and *Giacomo Joyce*," paper presented at Omniscientific Joyce: The 27th International James Joyce Symposium, online conference, June 15, 2021. The paper was delivered as a prerecorded talk, which is available on YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RBVqWE1Of34/>. I spoke about the association copies and their implications for Ricchetti Randegger's relationship with Joyce on the same panel; Ronan Crowley, "Who? Beatrice," paper presented at Omniscientific Joyce: The 27th International James Joyce Symposium, online conference, June 15, 2021.

24. In addition to his paper at the 27th International James Joyce Symposium, Schneider has also presented "'Sorrrows of the Biografiend': Bice Ricchetti Randegger, Richard Ellmann, and the 'Who?' of *Giacomo Joyce*," paper presented at the 26th Trieste Joyce School, Trieste, Italy, July 2, 2024.

25. Details of the admissions register for 1912 at Archivio–Sanatorio Triestino were shared by Schneider. See also his "Being Bice" talk on YouTube.

26. See Joyce, *James Joyce's Letters to Sylvia Beach, 1921–1940*, ed. Melissa Banta and Oscar A. Silverman (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 1987), 104–5. The item is misidentified as a subscription list of "possible buyers for the Egoist edition of *Ulysses*." Future citations will be indicated parenthetically in the text as *JJSB*, followed by page number.

27. Lillian or Lilian Wallace (1885–1962) is another of the transnational women whose lives intersected with Joyce's in the expatriate circles of interwar Paris. Born Emma Louisa Southern in Saltburn, Yorkshire, she worked as a dancer in Paris before marrying Richard Wallace, an American commercial artist, in 1913. Both were active in the American Red Cross during the First World War and part of Joyce's social circle by the early 1920s. See John Simpson, "Lillian Wallace," *James Joyce's Correspondence*, June 13, 2022, <https://jamesjoycecorrespondence.org/>.

28. In an earlier version of this material, Ellmann leans more heavily into Santas: "Mrs. Santos [*sic*] in figure and conduct modeled the mature Molly" ("Backgrounds of *Ulysses*" 380). In the interim between his early essay and the first edition of the biography, Ellmann gained access to *Giacomo Joyce* and, learning of Popper—that Swiss Army knife of female character originals—redirected his research away from Santas toward a new candidate for Molly.

29. See Manto Aravantinou, *Ta hellēnika tou Tzaiēms Tzous* (Athens: Hermes, 1977) or, in French translation, Aravantinou, "James Joyce et ses amis grecs," in *James Joyce*, ed. Jacques Aubert and Fritz Senn (Paris: Éditions de l'Herne, 1985), 58–64.

30. The record of their marriage appears in the Registro dei Matrimoni (1909), Archivio della Comunità Greco-Orientale di Trieste. Archival research on the Santas family in Trieste was generously undertaken and shared by Schneider.

31. The Evakuierung or evacuation register for May–July 1915 is Archivio di Stato di Trieste (AST)–Polizia Riservata (b. 450).

32. The discrepancy is revealed by comparing the Santas family returns in Censimento (1910), Archivio Storico del Comune di Trieste, with the family’s Registerkarte or registration card in the Stadtarchiv Zürich.

33. “Nikola Santos [*sic*] was illiterate, but could recite many long passages of the *Odyssey* learned by ear”; Frank Budgen, *James Joyce and the Making of “Ulysses”* (London: Grayson & Grayson, 1934), 174.

34. The Santas family’s relocations can be traced through letters they wrote to Antoni Rubió i Lluch, honorary Greek consul in Barcelona, between 1917 and 1924. The letters are summarized in Antoni Rubió i Lluch, *Epistolari grec*, ed. Eusebi Ayensa i Prat, vol. 4, 1916–36 (Barcelona: Institut d’Estudis Catalans, 2012). I am grateful to Eusebi Ayensa i Prat for generously sharing photocopies of the Santases’ correspondence.

35. See Robert E. Scholes, *The Cornell Joyce Collection: A Catalogue* (Ithaca, N.Y.: Cornell University Press, 1961), 179.

36. Box XVIII.E.1, Folder 8 in the James Joyce Collection, University at Buffalo, is a list of recipients for the Shakespeare and Company *Ulysses* prospectus in the hands of Joyce and Lucia.

37. Brenda Maddox, *Nora: The Real Life of Molly Bloom* (Boston: Houghton Mifflin, 1988), 198.

38. Marina Warner, *Monuments & Maidens: The Allegory of the Female Form* (London: Weidenfeld and Nicolson, 1985), 277.

39. Brenda Maddox, “Excavating Nora,” in *Biography & Autobiography: Essays on Irish and Canadian History and Literature*, ed. James Noonan (Ottawa: Carleton University Press, 1993), 82.

40. Both Ellmann and Maria Jolas referred to the family papers in this way. See William S. Brockman, “Learning to be James Joyce’s Contemporary? Richard Ellmann’s Discovery and Transformation of Joyce’s Letters and Manuscripts,” *Journal of Modern Literature* 22, no. 2 (Winter 1998–99): 258–59.

41. Zachary Leader, *Ellmann’s Joyce: The Biography of a Masterpiece and Its Maker* (Cambridge, Mass.: The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2025), 272.

42. The Solange and Stephen James Joyce Collection, bequeathed to the University of Reading in 2020, would have been the most likely repository for Nora’s side of the 1909 correspondence but apparently contains no trace of it.